

Influence of planting method and planting density on dry matter yield and some yield parameters of *S. rostrata* biofertilizer.^a

Treatment	Density	Plant height (cm)	Branches/plant (no.)	Dead plants/m ² (no.) ^b	Dry weight (t/ha)
<i>5-wk-old plants</i>					
Seeding	20 kg/ha	39 e	1 c	na	0.15 d
	40 kg/ha	41 e	1 c	na	0.41 bc
	80 kg/ha	37 e	1 c	na	0.55 bc
20-cm cutting	25/m ²	52 de	1.2 bc	3.2 bc	0.41 bc
	50/m ²	62 d	1.3 bc	7.1 ab	0.64 c
	100/m ²	76 c	1.3 bc	8.2 a	1.09 c
30-cm cutting	25/m ²	82 bc	1.9 a	1.2 c	0.89 c
	50/m ²	92 ab	1.5 b	2.6 c	2.31 b
	100/m ²	101 a	1.3 b	3.4 b	3.51 a
<i>7-wk-old plants</i>					
Seeding	20 kg/ha	85 e	1d	na	0.72 e
	40 kg/ha	87 de	1d	na	1.54 d
	80 kg/ha	104 d	1d	na	2.60 c
20-cm cutting	25/m ²	120 c	1.1 cd	2.9 bc	1.20 d
	50/m ²	125 c	1.2 c	6.2 ab	1.64 d
	100/m ²	146 b	1.4 b	8.3 a	3.48 bc
30-cm cutting	25/m ²	148 b	1.8 a	1.5 c	2.19 c
	50/m ²	165 a	1.3 b	2.5 c	4.31 b
	100/m ²	178 a	1.1 c	4.6 b	6.23 a

^a Duncan's multiple range test at 0.05. ^b na = data not available.

N accumulation in *S. rostrata*.

Plot size was 12 m². Stem cuttings of 8-wk-old plants were pushed about 5 cm deep into newly plowed and water-saturated soil (pH [KCl] 6.3, 1.1% organic C, 0.121% total N, 18.5 ppm P Olsen), 1.44 meq exchangeable K/100 mg CEC 33.9 meq/100 g). Plants were harvested at 5 and 7 wk.

Increasing planting rate resulted in increased biomass and N production. Cuttings showed faster growth and more dry matter and N production than seeds (see table and figure). Highest biomass and N yield were with 30-cm-long cuttings. They exhibited lower mortality and more branching than 20-cm-long

cuttings. To accumulate the same amount of N/ha, 30-cm-long cuttings require about 2 wk less growth than seeded plants. Only about 2-3 kg of seeds may be needed to produce enough plants for cuttings to plant 1 ha.

Broadcast seeding rate is 25-40 kg seeds/ha.

Although additional labor is needed to make and plant cuttings, it may be economical compared to seeding because it requires less seed, water management, and land preparation. Plants for cuttings might be grown on dikes and borders. □

Effect of sesbania green manure and wheat straw on ammonia volatilization loss in wetland soil

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Attempts are being made to identify short-duration leguminous green manure (LGM) crops that can be inserted into intensified cropping systems. High-yielding cultivars also leave large amounts of residue, which is either burned or incorporated into soil.

Crop residues and LGM may influence transformations of applied N. We studied the effect of sesbania green manure and wheat straw on ammonia volatilization from urea, in a laboratory study using the forced-draft chamber technique.

Ten pots (10 liters) containing 7 kg air-dry soil (pH 10.0, 0.35% organic C, 0.07% total N, and CEC 9.5 meq/100 g) were flooded, puddled, and preincubated with 1 cm standing water for 1 wk. Soil was then fertilized with 26 mg P/kg as single superphosphate and 50 mg K/kg as muriate of potash.

Treatments were N as urea alone or in combination with *Sesbania aculeata* green manure or wheat straw. N was applied at 100 and 200 kg N/ha. Finely chopped 2-mo-old fresh sesbania (2.5% N dry weight) was incorporated at

1. Effect of sesbania green manure and wheat straw on ammonia volatilization in flooded Ludhiana soil, India.

2. Effect of sesbania green manure and wheat straw on floodwater NH₄⁺-N concentration. Ludhiana, India.

30 t/ha. Wheat straw (<2 mm) was incorporated at 7.5 t/ha.

Soil was reflooded and evaporation losses were replenished daily, to

maintain 5 cm standing water. Floodwater temperatures ranged from 28.5 to 33 °C. Two pots/treatment were fitted with chambers continuously flushed with NH₃-free compressed air.

Soil test fertilizer recommendations increase economic yields of rice

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We compared bases for N application recommendations—state, soil test, and farmers' practice in a farmer's field during 1986.

Soil of the experimental field was sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH (1:2) 8.4, 0.36% organic C, EC (1:2) 0.10 dS/m, CEC 10.9 meq/100 g soil, 190 kg available N/ha (alkaline permanganate method), 8.0 kg available P/ha (NaHCO₃ extract), and 305 kg available K (ammonium acetate extract)/ha. Available Zn was 0.5 ppm (DTPA

NH₃ that evolved from incubated samples was collected at intervals using a manifold, and estimated by absorbing in 2% boric acid-mixed indicator solution. Floodwater samples also were taken to analyze NH₄⁺-N.

Rate of N loss by ammonia volatilization in flooded soil was markedly affected by type of amendment (Fig. 1). Incorporating wheat straw resulted in the greatest N loss due to volatilization. At 16 d, cumulative ammonia volatilization was 11% for wheat straw + N, 4.5% for N alone, and 1% for green manure + N.

No ammonia volatilization occurred in the soil amended with green manure alone. In the soil amended with wheat straw, NH₃ volatilization could already be detected at 2 d, the first sampling.

Ammoniacal N concentration in the floodwater was greatest in soil amended with wheat straw + N (Fig. 2).

These results suggest that higher N losses through ammonia volatilization in straw-amended soil were probably due to the high rate of urea application. Incorporation of wheat straw may have changed the urease kinetic parameters, which seem dependent on the organic material incorporated. □

extractable). Nutrient limits used for recommendations were as follows:

	Nutrient limits (kg/ha) (elemental form)			
	N	P	K	Zn(ppm)
Low	<250	<5	<125	<0.6
Medium	250-500	5-10	125-300	
High	>500	>10	>300	

Seedlings of PR106 (30-35 d) duration were transplanted. Each treatment received the following nutrients:

	Nutrients (kg/ha) (elemental form)			
	N	P	K	ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O
State recommendation	125	26.20	50	25
Soil test recommendation	125	17.47	-	-
Farmers' practice	125	-	-	-

One-third N and all the P, K, Zn were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was applied in 2 equal splits at 3 and